

Software at NASA: Lightning Breakout 1A

Mission-related software: Part 1

Mission Operations Automation with GMSEC:

A Presentation on Software Automation

May 7-9, 2024

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Software Engineering Division

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For more information, scan the barcode or click here :

<https://tinyurl.com/3z3vp2ev>

GMSEC's Mission Benefits

GMSEC General Information

GMSEC was established in 2001 to coordinate ground and flight data systems development and services at GSFC. It has been operational since 2005.

Goals

- Simplify development, integration and testing
- Facilitate technology infusion over time
- Support evolving development and operational concepts
- Allow for mix of heritage, COTS and new components while avoiding vendor lock-in

Concepts

- Standardize interfaces – not components
- Provide a middleware infrastructure
- Allow users to choose – GMSEC does not decide which components are best or dictate which components a mission must use. It's the mission/user's choice!

GMSEC Automation Benefits

The architecture enables new approaches for automation

- Can "listen" for status from all components → situational awareness
- Can direct actions of components in a standardized way → system-wide control
- Recognize status and respond → event-driven automation

GMSEC allows for monitoring of:

- temperature, humidity, disk usage, etc. for GSFC control centers.
- Spacecraft Telemetry

Visualization Tools show network performance, system configuration, processing status and spacecraft telemetry.

FEB 03 2023 00:03:25 UTC

SERVER: ONLINE DATABASE: ONLINE

BEACONS SATELLITES TERMINALS OVERLAYS

BEACONS

ALL ELT EPIRB PLB ANSEL OTHER

SEARCH

BEACON ID	PACKET RECEIVED	TRACK
0BE14CCCF45CE99999999999	FEB 02 2023 23:02:50 UTC	●
0BE14CCCF443E99999999999	FEB 02 2023 23:58:10 UTC	●
0B787337328AAAAA	FEB 03 2023 00:00:40 UTC	●
0B677AAA32299999999999	FEB 02 2023 23:14:10 UTC	●
0B477AF72332039999999999	FEB 02 2023 23:01:59 UTC	●
0B477AF72332039999999999	FEB 02 2023 21:16:48 UTC	●
0B477AF72332039999999999	FEB 03 2023 00:00:59 UTC	●
0B477AF72332039999999999	FEB 02 2023 23:28:09 UTC	●
0B477AAA32299999999999	FEB 02 2023 23:53:10 UTC	●
0B474CCF8132E99999999999	FEB 02 2023 23:58:25 UTC	●
0B474CCF8131E99999999999	FEB 02 2023 23:57:35 UTC	●
0AE14000400183333333333	FEB 03 2023 00:00:40 UTC	●
0ABF77FC8801F00000000000	FEB 02 2023 18:20:05 UTC	●
0ABF77FC8203F00000000000	FEB 03 2023 00:02:35 UTC	●
0ABF77FC8202F04000000000	FEB 02 2023 22:20:55 UTC	●

SHOWING 241 OF 241 BEACONS

TOOLS

LAT 35.9465 LON -24.3728

0A797FFC76F00000000000

TYPE	POSITION	ALTITUDE	TIMESTAMP
ENCODED	34.6825, -120.5520	N/A	FEB 03 2023 00:00:19 UTC
MERGED	34.6823, -120.5556	0.0463 MI	FEB 03 2023 00:00:47 UTC
BURST	34.6843, -120.5518	0.0388 MI	FEB 03 2023 00:00:45 UTC

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307	34.6825, -120.5520	N/A	FEB 02 2023 23:58:39 UTC
306	34.6825, -120.5520	N/A	FEB 02 2023 23:57:49 UTC
305	34.6825, -120.5520	N/A	FEB 02 2023 23:56:59 UTC

0A797FFC76F00000000000

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MERGED	53.3144, -60.4877	0.0200 MI	FEB 03 2023 00:00:47 UTC
BURST	53.3149, -60.4580	0.0006 MI	FEB 03 2023 00:00:47 UTC

HISTORY: OFF

TRACKER 2

SEARCH & RESCUE INTELLIGENT TERMINAL (SAINT) interface showing a satellite track map and data tables.

SEARCH & RESCUE INTELLIGENT TERMINAL (SAINT)

Revolutionizing Search and Rescue Operations

NASA GODDARD SPACE FLIGHT CENTER

Stephan J. Wlodarczyk / 583
Shannon D. Bull / 583

- SAINT supports NASA, national, and international beacon testing activities, as well as human spaceflight missions.
- Modernizes the search and rescue data dissemination processes, providing NASA personnel with insight into beacon locations, shortening the timeline required for space capsule and astronaut recovery during emergencies.
- Revolutionizes the government-furnished capability for evaluating effects of radio-frequency interference on SAR geolocation data.
- Promotes rapid detection and location of beacons worldwide, particularly in areas with reduced global navigation satellite system (GNSS) coverage.
- Serves as a portal for user engagement with Big Datasets, bolstering NASA's ability to uncover impacts on a real-world operational system that saves lives daily.

Automated Data Processing and Data Quality Analysis Pipelines for the DART DRACO Instrument

2024 NASA SMD Software Workshop

Dany Waller, Ray Espiritu, Hari Nair, Terik Daly, Carolyn Ernst, Olivier Barnouin, Nancy Chabot, Andrew Rivkin, and the DART Investigation Team

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DRACO Data Pipeline Philosophy

Minimize time between data downlink and high-quality data products being made available through the Science Operations Center.

Develop autonomous pipeline using Nextflow to process and format data into raw and calibrated PDS4 products using Python and Java tools.

During the impact event, the data processing pipeline produced 25 raw images per second and 15 calibrated images per second.

Develop autonomous pipeline using Nextflow to check data quality of raw and calibrated PDS4 product using Python tools.

In total, 259,290 raw products and 246,566 calibrated products were verified and validated, and delivered to NASA's Planetary Data System in 2023.

The marslab ecosystem of tools for reproducible multispectral remote sensing

Chase Million¹, Michael St. Clair¹, Sierra V. Brown¹, Sabrina A. Curtis¹, Melissa Rice²

1. Million Concepts LLC (chase@millionconcepts.com, mstclair@millionconcepts.com), 2. Western Washington University

<https://github.com/MillionConcepts/marslab-reference>

10⁶C Million Concepts

marshlab is an ecosystem of analysis software for remote sensing data, with a special emphasis on multispectral observations of Mars. It includes both "applications" (discrete user-facing programs designed to support specific workflows) and "infrastructure" (support code ranging from language frameworks to format definitions to reference implementations of spectral parameter calculations). The applications are designed to be *focused*: each one has a specific purpose, attempts to accomplish that purpose well, and eschews feature creep. They are also designed to be *interoperable*: by using common exchange formats, they can collectively support an extremely wide variety of data processing, exploration, analysis, and presentation tasks.

Infrastructure

[marshlab](#): the ecosystem's core support library. It defines common formats, shared references, and standardized methods for common batch image processing tasks such as cropping, statistical analysis, and geometric transformation. Highlights include Look, a lightweight construction kit for multispectral visualizations; and BandSet, an object that simplifies multispectral image processing by allowing users to treat image clusters as single objects. Its high-level objects can be configured for many data sets, and its low-level features are generically useful to non-*marshlab* software in similar domains.

[planetary data reader](#): provides a streamlined Pythonic interface to all observational data and metadata stored in the Planetary Data System.

[dustgoggles](#): abstract tools and light frameworks that solve software engineering problems in other *marshlab* libraries but do not implement science domain logic. Because it is not domain-specific, it is also suitable for supporting thematically-unrelated libraries outside the ecosystem.

Applications

[VISOR](#): the **V**isual-**I**nfrared **S**pectral **br**OWse**R** is a search engine and interactive graphing app for reflectance spectra. It has special capabilities to help researchers find laboratory spectra similar to remote sensing observations. The app runs in a browser, and an instance is live at <https://www.westernreflectancelab.com/visor/>.

[asdf](#): this application provides functions that allow users to archive spectral data files by keysmashing **a-s-d-f**. It streamlines last-mile processing for observational data by converting them into common interchange formats, concatenating them with metadata from many sources, calculating derived parameters, rendering a host of visualizations, and sending all of these products to shared data repositories. It is in tactical use on Mars 2020 Mastcam-Z and also used for analysis on MSL Mastcam. We are unfortunately unable to make an implementation of *asdf* publicly available at this time due to mission nondisclosure rules.

[MultiDEX](#): the **M**ultispectral **D**ata **E**xplorer allows users to rapidly search on and visualize arbitrary parameters across large multispectral datasets. The *marshlab* infrastructure makes it easily extensible to new datasets. It is in active tactical use on Mars 2020 Mastcam-Z and Mars Science Laboratory Mastcam, and has beta support for MSL ChemCam and M20 SuperCam.

Developing software package for Lunar Environment Heliospheric X-ray Imager

Ramiz A. Qudsi, Boston University

<https://github.com/Lexi-BU/lexi>

Image the motion of the dayside magnetopause

Image courtesy:
Cadin Connor, BU

1.1 LEXI package description

LEXI package has the following functions:

- `get_spc_prams`
- `get_exposure_maps`
- `get_sky_backgrounds`
- `get_lexi_images`

<https://slides.com/qudsi/lexi>

Sample Function

```
def get_lexi_images(  
    ... time_range: list = None,  
    ... time_zone: str = "UTC",  
    ... interp_method: str = "linear",  
    ... time_step: float = 5,  
    ... ra_range: list = [0, 360],  
    ... dec_range: list = [-90, 90],  
    ... ra_res: float = 0.1,  
    ... dec_res: float = 0.1,  
    ... time_integrate: float = None,  
    ... background_correction_on: bool = True,  
    ... save_exposure_map_file: bool = False,  
    ... save_exposure_map_image: bool = False,  
    ... save_sky_backgrounds_file: bool = False,  
    ... save_sky_backgrounds_image: bool = False,  
    ... save_lexi_images: bool = False,  
    ... verbose: bool = True,  
):
```

Open-Source Principles Utilized by the CERES Edition 5 Level-3 Framework

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CERES Data Management Team, NASA LaRC Science Directorate

<https://science.larc.nasa.gov>

<https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov>

Poster with Additional Info

<https://tinyurl.com/3bad2sjt>

Open-Source Principles Utilized by the CERES Edition 5 Level-3 Framework

Clouds and the Earth's
Radiant Energy System

CERES Level 3 working group leads' goals for the Edition 5 framework maintainability improvements:

Greater Modularity

Configurable

Rapid Analysis

Easier and faster to configure experimental test runs. More rapid feedback to science team.

CERES Edition 5 data products are currently under development. Edition 5 products include both scientific improvements and behind-the-scenes enhancements for code maintainability.

Edition 5 Framework Proof of Concept:
CRS1deg-Hour (Edition 4A)
Product released to public: March 28, 2024

Modularity improvements include:

- Migrating Fortran-90 codebase to Object Oriented languages:
 - Fortran 2018
 - C++17
- Implementing single purpose algorithms and functions
 - increasing reusability
- Increasing the usage of unit testing
 - using doctest for C++
- Migrating aspects of product definition to JSON configuration files

```
{ "prop": 0, "propname": "surface_pressure", "valmin": 0.0, "valmax": 1100.0, "valdef": 3.4928235e+38, "units": "hPa", "avescheme": "normal", "weightproperty": "None", "leg_type": "None", "linked_property": "None", "gridding": "Gridded", "coverage_content_type": "physicalMeasurement" }
```

JSON-based Configuration

- Reduces the need for hard-coded elements
- Configuration parameters includes:
 - valid ranges for datasets
 - variable weight/scaling factors
 - gridding layout
 - attributes for data variables
 - algorithm selection (binning, etc.)

The Edition 4A CERES Cloud Radiative Swath (CRS) 1deg-Hour data product generator used as a proof-of-concept for the Edition 5 Level 3 framework.

Framework showed positive results aiding in maintainability and reusability for use in future Edition 5 data products generators.

Talk 7

WITHDRAWN

Open-Source Software Development for the Roman Space Telescope Coronagraph Instrument

Authors: Roman Coronagraph Community Participation Team,
Simulations and Data Reduction Working Group

Co-Leads Max Millar-Blanchaer & Jason Wang
presented by Ellis Bogat (ebogat@umd.edu)

Full slide deck:

<https://zenodo.org/records/11122394>

Summary

- The **Roman Space Telescope Coronagraph Instrument** is a technology demonstration which will enable the direct imaging of exoplanets in visible, reflected light for the first time.
- The **Roman Coronagraph Community Participation Team (CPP)** is responsible for delivering the data reduction pipeline to process calibration and science data.
- The CPP is developing the pipeline **corgiDRP** with the following design principles:
 - **Modularity:** Pipeline will be comprised of stand-alone step functions, which operate on the dataset. These steps can be called manually or via a recipe template.
 - **Flexibility:** Pipeline steps should be agnostic to exact observation sequences and able to run in any order, to make it easy to add custom steps and expand functionality.
 - **Accessibility:** It should be easy to contribute code to the project! Inputs to step functions are simple and readable, and data formats are standardized using classes.
- Community development of corgidrp development enables investment & feedback from the community, early career opportunities to get involved with Roman science, and preparation for real data in 2027!

Open-Source Science-Driven Development of the Science Data System (SDS) for Earth System Observatory (ESO) Atmospheric Missions

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11122562](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11122562)

• Open-Source Science

- The ESO Atmosphere Observing System (AOS) mission Science Data System (SDS) will **support the NASA SMD SPD-41a policy** by openly sharing software, data and publications to the maximum extent legally permitted.

• SDS Framework

- The Adaptive Processing System (APS) components and AOS science algorithm software will **follow NASA's two-step software release process** for the New Technology Reporting (NTR) and Software Release System (SRS).

• Science Data

- The AOS SDS will **use a DAAC-centric model** for Cloud data storage and distribution.

• Science Code

- Publicly released software will be **shared immediately** and any user can **obtain a NASA Guest account** to make AOS mission software contributions.

• Community Engagement

- The AOS SDS will **promote use of open-source science** within AOS for sharing software, data and knowledge in an open and timely manner.

ZIGGY, AN OPEN-SOURCE APPLICATION FOR DATA ANALYSIS PIPELINES

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Detailed materials at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11111264>

Software for the NASA Science
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ziggy handles all the not-science and lets the scientists get on with the science!

Science data pipelines need to do a lot more than science:

- Logging
- Execution flow
- Execution monitoring
- Data accountability
- Configuration management
- Error handling
- And much more!

xkcd.com. Used under terms of Creative Commons License 2.5.

Ziggy Deployment Architecture

Ziggy is Lightweight

Develop here* ...

... deploy here!

*Dog not included.

Software for the NASA SMD Workshop
May 7 - 9, 2024

A managed Services Approach to Mission Data Processing Systems

Presented by: Luke Dahl
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Jet Propulsion Laboratory
California Institute of Technology

Managed Service Data Processing System

- Project teams focus on science and project requirements
- Leverage a dedicated team of experts for most common needs
- Integrate through standards and common interfaces

Forging a Path to Multi-Institution, Open-Source Mission Software for Science

Can we really make multi-institution data processing pipelines for missions?

Jon Vandegriff, JHU / APL, jon.vandegriff@jhuapl.edu

Greg Lucas, CU Boulder / LASP, Greg.Lucas@lasp.colorado.edu

Point 1: A pile of software thrown over the open source fence will not result in cohesive mission data systems.

Point 2: A grass-roots effort in Heliophysics is underway to coordinate science pipelines for missions. Join us!

White Paper on Heliophysics
Science Data System Coordination

Full
Presentation

<https://doi.org/10.3847/25c2cfcb.1c21b704> <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11114328>

Pathways to Multi-Institution Science Data Systems

Ok

Throw over the fence
in open-source pile

Better

Find low hanging fruit
of sharable elements

Best

Jointly develop community
library based on shared
concepts and interfaces

Question Box:

How do we lower barriers to
cross-institution adoption
of mission pipelines?

What are your open-source,
re-usable science data system
elements?

What are the key interfaces
in a data science pipeline?

Key Community Needs

- Establish a Heliophysics Data and Software Working Group
- Create a shared vocabulary, interfaces and ultimately code elements for pipelines
- Funded reasons to work together (missions do not pay for generification)
- Establish cross-disciplinary (cross-division) coordination mechanisms

(images on this page generated using AI within Adobe Illustrator 2024)